

An Analysis of Inequalities in Education in Telangana State

K. Anji Reddy

Associate professor of Economics
Mahatma Gandhi University
Nalgonda, Telangana State.

Abstract:- Inequality persists in every sphere of human society but these inequalities have to be at minimum level adjustable by the society. Despite several efforts made by the governments to reduce the inequalities instead of decreasing income inequalities, they are increasing in the recent past. Inequalities in literacy by gender and social category wise are reduced to a greater extent but still they continue to exist. In equalities in gross enrolment ratios at school education level almost eliminated but SCs dropout rate is much less than STs and others. In equalities in learning levels do exist at school education level between gender, social category, rural-urban and subject wise. Gross enrolment ratios at higher education level Telangana state is doing far better than all India ratios, in equalities in gender are reduced significantly in fact SCs girls GER is higher than boys and also other social categories too. Equity in financing of education among social categories and different levels of education reduced but still exists. After the formation of the Telangana state the government spending has increased substantially in every sector of the economy and education also received increased funding. But these increased funding is not commensurate with increasing demand. Therefore, the government has to increase government spending substantially to increase the human capital and incomes of the people by providing quality of education to reduce all kinds' inequalities in education and society. The present paper is divided into five sections. First section deals with how inequalities are exist in the present society. Inequalities in literacy, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), enrolment, dropout at school level and higher education are presented in section two and in section three analyzed inequalities in learning by gender, social groups and rural-urban. In section four examined inequalities in financing of education by different levels of education and social groups and summary and conclusions are made in last section.

Keywords:- *Inequality, Social Group, Literacy, Learning Level, Financing*

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years rising inequalities in the society are indeed becoming an important concern of all and have seen a rise in interest in understanding trends and dimensions of inequality across countries as well as within countries and in different sectors. International institutions like the World

Bank, International Monetary Fund and Asian Development Bank have paid attention to look into the nature and consequences of rising inequality across and within countries for growth and poverty reduction. The United Nations has also included inequality reduction as one of the Sustainable Development Goals-10. While much of the discussion of inequality has revolved around trends in inequality across nations and within developed countries, it has also changed its focus, from inequality as a purely empirical and distributional issue to the changing nature of inequality and its impact on growth and mobility. The rise in inequality is not just in terms of its impact on future economic growth and distribution, but also in terms of social and political stability in a country such as India, which has a high level of horizontal inequalities based on caste, class, religion, race, gender, and location. Horizontal inequalities are embedded in social and political structures and affect citizens' access to basic services.

India is becoming known for very poor on one side and world wealthiest people (For example Mukesh Ambani with wealth of 84.5 billion US dollars occupied 10th richest person place in Forbes Worlds billionaires list in 2021) on other side and leading to high inequalities in the country. According world Inequality report top 1 per cent holds 22 per cent of national income, top 10 per cent people holds 57 per cent of the total National Income while the bottom 50 per cent people share is just 13 per cent in 2021. According to the report, middle class is relatively poor with an average wealth of only Rs.7,23,930/ or 29.5 per cent of the total income, as compared with the top 10 per cent and 1 per cent who own 65 per cent (Rs. 63,54,070) and 33 per cent (Rs.3,24,49,360) respectively. The average national income of the Indian adult population is Rs. 2,04,200 in 2021. The bottom 50 per cent earned is Rs. 53,610, while the top per cent earned over 20 times more (Rs.11,66,520), the report states. The average household wealth in India is Rs. 9,83,010, with the bottom 50 per cent owning almost nothing, with an average wealth of 6 per cent of the total Rs. 66,280/.

The Multi-dimensional Poverty Index (MPI) is constructed by NitiAayog by using the data of National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4) conducted in the year 2014-15 and NFHS-5 conducted in 2019-20. They have used mainly information of 12 indicators by assigning appropriate weights to them. Education is one of the indicators to build the MPI with weightage of 1/3 in which 1/6 weightage to the average years of school completion and 1/6 to child

attendance to school. So, it indicates the weightage given to the education in constructing Multi-dimensional Poverty Index, since, the education is determining poverty, income, standard of living, reduces the economic inequalities in society.

As per the recent Multi-dimensional Poverty Index (MPI) prepared by NitiAayog, one in every four people in India was multidimensional poor. Bihar has the highest proportion of people (51.91 per cent of the state's population) who are multidimensional poor, followed by Jharkhand at 42.16 per cent and Uttar Pradesh at 37.79 per cent. The best performing states in MPI are Kerala (0.71%), Goa (3.76%), Sikkim (3.82%), Tamil Nadu (4.89) and Punjab (5.59) in India.

While Telangana State occupies 19th rank with 13.76% MPI score, but within the state there are wide variations between districts in MPI score. Hyderabad district with a complete urban population with lowest MPI score of 4.2 per cent of people lives in poverty, on the other hand Adilabad district with almost rural population has highest MPI score of

27.4 per cent of people lives in poverty, followed by Mahaboobnagar 26.11 per cent, Nizamabad 21.44 per cent, Medak 17.9 per cent and Nalgonda 15.3 per cent.

Education expansion acts as a major factor in reducing prevailing high inequality that is an increase in average years of schooling results in more equal distribution of income. Education expansion should be used as a powerful tool to mitigate income inequality by emphasizing the quality of education.

When education reduces the economic inequalities in society, first of all are there equalities in education in terms of literacy, gender, Age, regional, social category, public financing, learning levels or not? This paper tries to examine these issues by using secondary sources of information. The present paper is organized into five sections. The first section covers introduction of inequalities and inequalities literacy, gender and region are presented in second section. Inequalities in learning are presented in third section, equity in financing presented in fourth section, summary and concluding observations are made in last section.

II. EQUITY IN LITERACY AND GDP

Generally, the literacy rates vary with age and gender they are no exceptions to the Telangana state. These particulars are presented in below table-1.

Age Group	Telangana		India	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
7-10	87.2	86.3	85.1	83.0
11-13	95.2	93.3	93.6	90.8
14-15	94.3	91.9	92.2	89.3
16-17	93.8	90.9	91.8	88.1
18-24	90.0	79.5	89.3	79.1
25-29	82.5	64.4	85.3	69.9
30-34	76.5	53.9	82.2	62.9
35-39	70.4	43.7	78.2	56.1
40-44	62.6	36.8	74.3	50.8
45-49	57.4	31.9	71.9	46.8
50-54	52.9	28.2	69.8	43.9
55-59	54.1	24.7	70.7	39.2
60-64	43.3	17.9	62.4	31.6
65-69	41.0	16.6	60.3	28.3
70-74	34.8	14.0	54.7	24.7
75-79	39.7	16.1	57.9	26.8
80 & above	40.6	19.0	53.5	26.2

Table 1:- Gender and Age Group wise Literacy rates in Telngana& India- 2011
Source: Census 2011

The analysis on gender and age-wise literacy rates for Telangana State revealed a higher literacy rate for the age group of 7–24 years for both male and female and it is higher than the all- India literacy rate of both male and female in the same age group. The data also shows a better situation in the state for males and females in the age group of 18–24 years at 90 per cent and 79.5 per cent respectively, and these figures are higher than the national average of 89.3 per cent and 79.1

(see Table-1) per cent respectively, for the corresponding age group and gender. Further, it shows that in Telangana, the younger generation is going to school or able to access education than their elders. The Male literacy rate is higher than female for all the age groups that mean there is large gap in literacy rate of male and female, but the differences are less in the younger age group and more in higher age group. This is due to several initiatives taken up by government to enroll

the children in school by opening new primary schools under district primary education programme (DPEP) and subsequently universalization of elementary education by implementing Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) scheme and education has become as an fundamental right.

Any form of inequality affects every member of the society. Economic inequality impacts the GDP per capita that may lead to poorer health conditions and illiteracy, further it may add to increasing crime rate, political instability and ultimately destabilize the society. Its members also become pessimistic and lose faith in the government and each other. Education inequality impacts on school completion rate, employment opportunity of individual, income earning capacity, standard of life.

There is a strong correlation between GDP of a country and its literacy rate. Thus an increased literacy will lead to an increased level of GDP and at the same time maintains a steady level of population growth so that country’s progress made faster. It is also observed from the data of district wise GDP and Literacy population of Telangana State that the district with higher the literacy rate are enjoying with higher GDP and districts with lower literacy rate suffering with lower GDP. It is reflecting in poverty, the higher literate population districts like Hyderabad 14.10%, and Ranga Reddy 16.2% of population of the state are having lower poverty ratios of 4.27 and 5.83% respectively and on other lower literate population districts like Adilabad 5.92% and Mahaboobnagar 8.41% of the state population are having higher poverty ratios of 27.43% and 26.11% (see table-2) respectively.

Districts of Telangana	Head count Ratio	Intensity	MPI
Adilabad	27.43%	46.03%	0.126
Hyderabad	4.27%	41.01%	0.018
Karimnagar	9.20%	41.10%	0.038
Khammam	13.75%	42.26%	0.058
Mahbubnagar	26.11%	43.54%	0.114
Medak	17.87%	42.68%	0.076
Nalgonda	15.34%	43.81%	0.067
Nizamabad	21.44%	44.51%	0.095
Rangareddy	5.83%	41.84%	0.024
Warangal	12.45%	40.50%	0.050
Telangana	13.74%	43.2%	0.059

Table 2:- Telangana Headcount Ratio, Intensity, MPI
Source; NITI AAYOG

By taking the data of district wise Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP) of Telangana State for the year 2019-20 and literacy rates of 2011, Lorenz curve constructed and Gini coefficient calculated and presented (see Chart no-1). It can be observed from the Lorenz curve that there is a gap between equalizer line and Lorenz curve but the gap is not too large. It means that there are differences between the districts in GDP but these differences very limited and it is supported by gini coefficient value 0.268.

Chart 1:- Lorenz Curve
Gini coefficient = 0.268942

Inequality in education contributes the most to overall inequality, followed by inequality in life expectancy, and income inequality in India (UNDP, various years). Educational inequality measured in terms of years of schooling, of course, is a partial reflection of overall inequality as it ignores differential quality of teaching-learning outcomes across institutions. Further, if gross attendance ratio (GAR as measured in NSSO surveys) at any level of education was considered, inequality index goes further north (Banergee, 2020).

The critical question from the equity point of view is: ‘Equality of what?’ The relevance of human capability formation for freedom suggests the need for innovative lines of investigation dealing with the development of cognitive and constructive powers (Sen, 2009, p. 234). This is a fundamental paradigmatic shift from the means of living to the actual opportunities a person has away from the notional equality of opportunities, which the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009 (henceforth, RTE Act) assures. Equity does not mean equality of capability that the society aims at, as Amartya Sen argues. The focus of the capability approach is that “can the person actually do these things or not?” (Sen, 2009, p. 307). Further, “An institution or a policy may well be defended not on the grounds that it enhances capability of equality, but for the reason that it expands the capabilities of all, even if there is no distributional gain” (Sen, 2009, p. 298). It is a momentous distinction to be recognized in the making of public policy beyond mere concerns about efficiency.

Since education has positive externalities (or, spill overs), Pareto efficiency condition is inapplicable. However, there may have the social choice dilemma in allocating public resources, first, between ‘expanding out’ and ‘expanding up’. Second, it is the dilemma between allocations in educational sector and other competing social sectors, such as, public health and poverty alleviation from the concern for efficiency, or for equity and social justice.

➤ *Enrolment at school:*

Gross enrolment ratio (GER) is one of the indicators to understand the equity in education that too in school education at primary level, upper primary and secondary level across different social categories is presented in table 3. The GERs at primary level is higher than 100 across all social categories but it is declining as move to higher levels of education, GER at elementary level is higher than the secondary level but less than the primary level. One important and good sign in development in education of Telangana State GER of SCs is surpassed all other categories of students at all levels of school education in 2019-20 (see table-3) but STs GER is still lagging behind of all other categories of students at elementary and secondary level. Still governments needs to take measures to improve their enrolment for their better future and reduce the poverty of ST population.

Classes	All	SC's	ST's
I-V	111.96	121.85	105.38
VI - VIII	97.46	99.41	91.86
IX – X	88.00	89.99	81.96

Table 3:- Gross Enrolment Ratio in Scholl Education in Telangana in 2019-20
Source: Socio Economic Survey

➤ *Dropout at School:*

Every year a large number of students drop out of school education in the state and country. This will hinder the economic and social well-being of those students and reduces the literacy rate of the country. Dropout rate are considered to be a great wastage in the education system, not only do many students leave school without acquiring basic skills, but their premature departure represents a significant waste of scarce education resources. It is a serious issue to the government in particular and society at large.

Classes	All	SC's	ST's
I-V	0.00	0.00	1.18
VI – VIII	0.00	0.21	1.26
I – X	12.29	10.32	11.06

Table 4:- Drop Out Rates in School Education in Telangana in 2019-20
Source: Socio Economic Survey

The dropout rate at primary stage is zero for all and SCs category but there is a dropout in STs category (1.18%). But at the secondary stage the dropout rate is significant in all the categories of students. It is 12.29 % for all categories of students, 10.32% for SCs and 11.06% of STs students (see table-4). Surprisingly SCs students dropout rate is less than all other category of students and higher for all category of students. This is due to several programs initiated by government to provide quality of education students at all most free cost in the state.

➤ *Enrolment at higher Education:*

Admissions at higher education are made by Telangana State Council of Higher Education (TSCHE) every year by conducting admission test and based on the test of score student and rule of reservation student is admitted in to different courses. Course and sex wise admissions made by TSCHE in the year 2018-19 presented in table-5.

Course	Male	Female	Total
Engineering	41.82	58.18	100 (48648)
Medical	26.98	73.02	100 (6594)
Teacher Edn	20.61	79.39	100 (9549)
Physical Edn	70.61	29.39	100 (1235)
Law	65.37	34.63	100 (4132)
MBA &MCA	50.19	49.81	100 (21767)
Post-Graduation	42.83	57.17	100 (5797)
Degree	46.69	53.31	100(203167)

Table 5:- Course and Sex wise % of students admitted in Telangana-2018-19

Source: TSCHE, Note Figure in parentheses are absolute figures admitted by government

It can observed from the table-5 that except physical education and Law where there is less students admitted and remaining all other courses admitted girls students outnumbered the boys students. This is due to mainly two reasons, one is Telangana government implementing the 33% reservations to women in admissions and second reason is parents sending their girls children across all sections of the society to higher education by expecting better future for their wards.

Year	2016-17		2019-20	
	Telangana	All India	Telangana	All India
ALL	0.88	0.94	1.05	1.01
SCs	0.95	0.93	1.23	1.05
STs	0.76	0.85	0.93	0.97

Table 6:- Gender Parity Index in Telangana & ALL India in Higher Education

Source: ASIHE 2019-20 & 2016-17.

Ratio of female to male values of given indicator is gender parity index (GPI). A GPI between 0.97 and 1.03 indicates parity between the genders. A GPI below 0.97 indicates a disparity in favour of males. A GPI above 1.03 indicates a disparity in favour of females (UNSECO).

The GPI for all the categories, SCs and STs were less than 0.97 in the year 2016-17. It implies the gender disparity was in favour of Male but by the year 2019-20 GPI increased more than 1.03 for all 1.05 and SCs category students 1.23 (see table-6) so the index of SCs in favour female where as in STs GPI 0.93 and it is in favour males.

According to Tilak the gender inequalities in higher education have been reduced substantially and there was good improvement in inequalities between scheduled and non-scheduled population but rural-urban inequalities are

high and have not diminished much; and inequalities between the rich and the poor are highly striking, and they have widened over the years.

Course	SC	ST	BC	OC	Total
Engineering	12.79	06.58	50.13	30.5	100 (48648)
Medical	18.47	07.52	56.36	17.38	100 (6594)
Teacher Edn	23.5	08.85	57.26	10.39	100 (9549)
Physical Edn	30.28	22.83	44.62	02.27	100 (1235)
Law	22.94	08.30	43.75	25.00	100 (4132)
MBA &MCA	13.35	02.75	60.88	23.02	100 (21767)
Post Gradu	18.99	07.35	55.77	17.89	100 (5797)
Degree	16.43	09.10	57.79	16.68	100(203167)

Table 7:- Social Category and Course wise % of students admitted in Telangana-2018-19
Source: TSCHE, Note Figure in parentheses are absolute figures admitted by government

Year	Telangana State			All India		
	Both	Male	Female	Both	Male	Female
2012-13	33.1	36.9	29.3	21.5	22.7	20.1
2013-14	35.5	38.6	32.4	23.0	23.9	22.0
2014-15	36.1	39.2	33.0	24.3	25.3	23.2
2015-16	36.3	39.3	33.4	24.5	25.4	23.5
2016-17	35.8	38.0	33.6	25.2	26.0	24.5
2017-18	35.7	37.1	34.2	25.8	26.3	25.4
2018-19	36.2	35.8	36.5	26.3	26.3	26.4
2019-20	35.6	34.8	36.4	27.1	26.9	27.3

Table 8:- Year wise Gross Enrolment Ratios for All & Sex for Telangana State & All India
Source: AISHE 2017-18 & 2019-20

Year	Telangana State			All India		
	Both	Male	Female	Both	Male	Female
2012-13	32.2	35.2	29.1	16.0	16.9	15.0
2013-14	35.4	37.4	33.4	17.1	17.7	16.4
2014-15	36.1	38.1	34.1	19.1	20.0	18.2
2015-16	36.1	38.1	34.2	19.9	20.8	19.0
2016-17	34.1	34.9	33.3	21.1	21.8	20.2
2017-18	31.5	30.6	32.4	21.8	22.2	21.4
2018-19	33.7	30.9	36.4	23.0	22.7	23.3
2019-20	32.5	29.1	35.8	23.4	22.8	24.1

Table 9:- Year wise Gross Enrolment Ratios for SCs & Sex for Telangana State & All India
Source: AISHE 2017-18 & 2019-20

Year	Telangana State			All India		
	Both	Male	Female	Both	Male	Female
2012-13	27.0	32.5	21.6	11.1	12.4	9.8
2013-14	30.8	36.3	25.3	11.3	12.5	10.2
2014-15	33.5	39.6	27.5	13.7	15.2	12.3
2015-16	33.9	39.2	28.7	14.2	15.6	12.9
2016-17	32.7	37.2	28.3	15.4	16.7	14.2
2017-18	29.4	32.3	26.6	15.9	17.0	14.9
2018-19	30.7	32.7	28.8	17.2	17.9	16.5
2019-20	30.2	31.3	29.1	18.0	18.2	17.7

Table 10:- Year wise Gross Enrolment Ratios for STs & Sex for Telangana State & All India
Source: AISHE 2017-18 & 2019-20

According to Tilak analysis, gross attendance ratio in higher education by economic status of the households shows wide variations. In 2007-08, the difference in the gross attendance ratio between poorest and richest families is 29.5 per cent and this gap has gone up to 43.5 per cent in 2013-14. The extent of rural-urban disparity in access to higher education is found to be highest among the richest households. Further, merely two per cent of the higher educated belong to the poorest households and 74 per cent the richest households in 2007-08 and these figures are 3.7 per cent and 62 per cent respectively in 2013-14. Men have a higher probability of attending higher education compared to women; others (other than scheduled population and backward classes), and Muslims have a lower probability, compared to their respective counterparts. Similarly rich income groups have a higher probability of attending higher education institutions than others. When we estimated regression equations by each quintile, results are similar with some important exceptions. The gender differences in the probability of attending higher education are statistically significant only among the first three expenditure quintiles which mean that poor households differentiate between male and female children in access to higher education, while the rich do not. The difference in the probability of participation between men and women narrows down as one move from

poorest to richest quintiles. Similarly, the effect of other individual and household factors (caste, location of the household, religion) varies widely for different quintile classes.

III. EQUITY IN LEARNING

Gender-wise Learning Levels: Gender-wise achievement scores are presented in Chart-2. There are no significant gender differences in achievement scores both in the state and at the national level. There is no specific pattern emerge from the data on gender-wise and grade wise achievement scores. In some instances, the girls performed better than boys. Subject wise differences are negligible except in Mathematics where boys' performance is better than girls. In all respects the performance of girls is better than boys in school education. GER for girls is more than boys and drop-out rate is less among girls than among boys. In terminal examinations (SSC/Intermediate) also girls' performance is better. In this respect public education system is able to address the educational needs of the girls. Research on achievement scores also observed that gender variations are less significant on the whole (Azim Premji, 2004). However, the private sector is biased against the girls in school education.

Chart 2:- Average Achievement by Gender, Class and Subject in Telangana and India, 2017. Source: NCERT(2017)

Social Groups: It becomes pertinent to note the difference in the performance of students of different social backgrounds. The data on achievement levels by social category indicate that children from certain social backgrounds perform better than children from other social

groups(Chart-3). ST Children are consistently underperforming compared to all other social groups in all grades and in all subjects. Compared to national average the performance of SCs and STs in Telangana is poor in language and the difference widens as they move to higher classes.

Social differences exist at every level including in literacy rates, GERs and Drop-out rates in the state. Literacy rate among STs is much less than Literacy rate among SCs and other groups. Female literacy rate (39%) among STs is nearly half the urban female literacy rate(75%). The GERs in school education are more for SCs than all other social groups where it is less for STs than all other groups. The public education is able address the educational needs of the SCs and STs to a greater extent but due to predominance of private

sector in education these groups are lagging behind many indicators of education development. For example, the percentage SC and ST students attending private schools is 45 and 24% in elementary stage and 39 and 39 at secondary stage, respectively. On the other hand, the percentage OBC and OCs students attending private schools is 55 and 89 in elementary stage and 53 and 83 at secondary stage, respectively(IIDS, 2018:Table-12.7 P.160)

Chart 3:- Average Achievement by Social Group and Class in Telangana and India 2017. Source: NCERT(2017)

Rural Urban Variation in Learning Levels: Though rural urban differences exist in many indicators of education no such differences are observed in achievement scores both at the state as well as at the national level (Chart-4). There is no specific pattern emerges from the data on grade wise achievement scores in rural and urban areas. At national level, in grade 8, the performance of rural children is better than urban children in all the subjects. Both Census and NSSO Reports suggest that urban areas are better in the provision of education to all groups, including SC/ST children compared to rural areas(IIDS,2018:Table-12.1 to 12.3 P.158).

Chart 4:- Average Achievement by Class, Subject and Location in Telangana and India 2017. Source: NCERT(2017)

IV. EQUITY IN FINANCING OF EDUCATION

There has been remarkable transformation of education in Telangana state by providing access to all sections of society with emphasis on poor socio-economic groups. Divergent educational institutions like local to Global Institutions offering education from KG to PG. When such development is taking place whether is it inclusive or not?

For ensuring equity in education at school level government has established good number of schools and admission in these schools is absolutely free to all sections of the society. Further, to provide better quality of education at free of cost special schools are set up exclusively for specific weaker section of the community. In addition to these the

students belong weaker sections of the society who are interested to study in reputed private schools their fee will be paid by the government under best available schools scheme. For higher education government has introduced a scheme called Reimbursement of Tuition Fee (RTF) and maintenance Fee (MTF) for those who study in private institutions where 90% of higher education is provided in private sector only. Government is supporting not only students pursuing higher education in private institutions but also those going abroad for studies.

To know the inequality in distribution of RTF & MTF among different Social category of students and their representation in education Lorenz curve is constructed and presented in Chart-5.

Chart 5:- RTF & MTF Distribution Among Students in 2017-18

Cumulative percentage of student measured on X axis and cumulative percentage of RTF & MTF measured on Y axis. The blue line (known as line of equality) in the chart indicates equal distribution of benefits and orange line explains actual distribution of RTF & MTF benefit among social category of students. From the curve it can be observed that though the Fee reimbursement is not equally distributed among different social category of students but their shares are very nearer to the equal distribution. Backward class and Minority students are enjoying little less than their actual share and schedule tribes, schedule castes and economically backward students enjoying a bit more than their share. This unequal distribution is mainly due to the government

condition of total reimbursement of tuition fee charged by private colleges is paid up to below ten thousand ranks secured by student in common admission test conducted by the government and students secured more than ten thousand ranks are paid a common fee decided by the government, rest of the fee has to borne by student only. The fee variations are more in professional courses particularly Medicine and Engineering. For example CBIT engineering college government approved course fee is Rs.1,13,500 per year. The student secured rank in EAMCET is more than 10000 rank, though student is eligible for fee reimbursement, he will be paid common fee of Rs 35000/ only and remaining fee of Rs78500 has to borne by the student only.

Social Category	% of Fee Income	% of Students	Cumulative % of Students	cumulative% of Fee income
RTF-BC	46.27	55.26	46.27	55.26
RTF-Min	8.59	9.97	54.86	65.23
RTF-ST	11.14	10.23	66.00	75.46
RTF-SC	23.51	17.99	89.51	93.45
RTF-EBC	10.49	6.55	100.00	100.00

Table 11:- Social category wise students and Fee income received by them-2017-18

Source: <https://finance.telangana.gov.in/budget-volumes.jsp&e-pass> website

To understand the equity in allocation of funds to the different social categories one year data may not reflect exact intension of the government in allotment of funds to respective categories to ensure the equity. Sometimes government may allot more funds to the one social category to enable the government to complete the project taken up for that particular category. By next year another social category

may be allotted more funds for development. Therefore, it is required at least 5 to 6 years of data to know how the equity is ensured to all the social groups. Since six budget allotments are available after formation of state we have taken six years budget allotment for each social category and totaled it then worked out share of each social category and presented in table-12 and Chart no-3.

Social Categories	Total Budget allotted in 9 years	Share of social category
Schedule Castes	4,422.56	19.87
Schedule Tribes	1888.02	8.48
Backward Classes	10,440.87	46.92
Minority	2,859.71	12.85
E B Cs	2,643.32	11.88
Total	22,254.48	100.00

Table 12:- Social category wise budget allocation in nine years and their relative shares

Source: <https://finance.telangana.gov.in/budget-volumes.jsp> & e-pass website

From the table-12 it is observed that the SCs are taking highest share of 34.52 percentage, followed by BCs with 31.24 percentage, Minority with 16.43 percentage, STs with 11.00 percentage and EBCs with 6.81 percentage. The reason for SCs taking highest share is that after formation of the Telangana state the government has sanctioned 130 new

residential schools in the year 2016-17 and 30 degree colleges in 2017-18 academic years, for providing facilities like lodging and boarding, teaching arrangements, infrastructure and other facilities to the students enrolled in these institutions obviously need to spend more expenditure.

Chart 6:- Budget Share of each Social Category in % in 6 years

Subsequently the residential schools to the other social groups i.e. STs, BCs and Minority have been sanctioned and they have also commenced functioning and expenditure of these groups increases in coming years. All these schools become fully operational the financial burden on state government increases substantially.

Further to understand equity among different social groups in providing of education we have examined budget actually spent rather than mere allocation. Because, many a times huge budget allotments are made but nothing is spent on them that is why we have taken actual amount spent on all social groups on residential schools during 2017-18 and calculated average expenditure on each student made by each type of residential school societies and presented in table-13.

Society	Actual spent on the society Rs.in Crores	Average expenditure per student in Rupees
TSWREIS	599.81	84028
TTWREIS	456.27	95924
MJPTBCREIS	125.57	63929
TMEIS	348.75	72933
Total	1530.40	82099

Table 13:- Society wise average expenditure per student in 2017-18

Source: <https://finance.telangana.gov.in/budget-volumes.jsp&e-pass> website

Telangana Tribal welfare residential school society (TTWREIS) is spending on an average per student expenditure Rs.95928/ during 2017-18 which is highest among all the residential societies. It followed by Telangana Social welfare society (TSWREIS) Rs. 84028/ and least spent by BC welfare society (MJPTBCREIS) Rs.63929/ and it followed by minority welfare society (TMEIS) Rs 72933/. Average student expenditure of these four societies put

together is Rs 82099/. Two societies(TTWREIS and TSWREIS) are spending more than the overall average expenditure per student.

Equity aspects are not only examined among different social groups but also among the different types of education. The details of expenditure like share of expenditure, per student expenditure are presented in table-14.

Level/Type of Education	Actual Amount spent (Rs.in Crores)	As % total	Per student Expenditure (Rupees)
School Education	10687.70	68.95	38132
Higher Education	1410.70	9.10	51838
Technical Education	343.09	2.21	141166
Medical Education	1235.63	7.97	800071
Agriculture Education	293.48	1.89	991486
Welfare Education	1530.40	9.87	82099
		100.0	

Table 14:- Education type wise share and average expenditure per student in 2017-18

Source: <https://finance.telangana.gov.in/budget-volumes.jsp&e-pass> website

Among all the types of education school education is taking loin share i.e. 68.95% with total amount of Rs,10687.7 crores and it followed by welfare education 9.87% with an amount of Rs.1530.4 crores and least share enjoyed by agriculture education 1.89% with an amount of Rs. 293.48 crores and next least enjoyed by technical education 2.21% with 343.09 crores. If we look at the average expenditure per student, the maximum amount is spent on agriculture education (Rs.991486) followed by medical education (Rs.800071). If we exclude the school education among all types of education it is higher education that spent least amount Rs.51838 per student per year. The loin share is going to school education due to constitutional obligation. Less is spent on Agriculture education and technical education because technical education is almost completely provided in private sector where as agriculture education though offered completely in public sector but only to limited students. Even spending on medical education is also not huge in view of its importance. There is a greater inequality among different types of education in spending money from public exchequer but it is not a good sign for the development of the society in the long run.

V. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Inequality persists in every sphere of human society but these inequalities have to be at minimum level adjustable by the society. Despite several efforts made by the governments to reduce the inequalities instead of decreasing income inequalities, they are increasing in the recent past. Inequalities in literacy by gender and social category wise are reduced to a greater extent but still they continue to exist. In equalities in gross enrolment ratios at school education level almost eliminated but SCs dropout rate is much less than STs and others. In equalities in learning levels do exist at school education level between gender, social category, rural-urban and subject wise. Gross enrolment ratios at higher education level Telangana state is doing far better than all India ratios, in equalities in gender are reduced significantly in fact SCs girls GER is higher than boys and also other social categories too. Equity in financing of education among social categories and different levels of education reduced but still exists. After the formation of the Telangana state the government spending has increased substantially in every sector of the economy and education also received increased funding. But these increased funding is not commensurate with increasing demand. Therefore, the government has to increase government spending substantially to increase the human capital and incomes of the people by providing quality of education to reduce all kinds' inequalities in education and society.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Banerjee, Debdas (2020). Inequality in Education: Aspects of Opportunities and Processes in India, *Artha Beekshan, Volume 28, No. 4 (March 2020), pp. 78-96*.
- [2]. Himanshu (2019). Inequality in India-A review of levels and trends, WIDER Working paper-42, United Nation University World Institute for Development Economic Research (wider.unu.edu).
- [3]. Kumar, Deepak & Pradeep Kumar Choudary, (2021). Do Private Schools really produce more learning than public Schools in India? Accounting for student's school absenteeism and the time spent on homework, *Journal Education Development, Volume 83, issue 1, May*.
- [4]. NITI Aayog (2021). INDIA National Multidimensional Poverty Index- Base line Report, NITI Aayog, Government of India, New Delhi.
- [5]. Reddy, Shiva. B and K. Anji Reddy (2019). "Is there A Learning Crisis in Telangana State?", Paper presented in Telangana Economics Association (TEA) third Annual Conference held at Osmania University, Hyderabad.
- [6]. Sen, A. (2009). *The Idea of Justice*. New York: Allen Lane.
- [7]. Shilpi's (2021). Education as the Great leveler? Not necessarily say new research, World Bank Feature story, November 30, 2021.
- [8]. Tilak, JBG, & Pradeep Kumar Choudhury (2019). Inequality in Access to Higher Education in India between the Poor and the Rich: Evidence from NSSO Data.
- [9]. http://www.ecineq.org/ecineq_paris19/papers_EcineqPSE/paper_178.pdf (accessed on 20-02-2022)